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SOME EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DATA CONCERNING COLORECTAL CANCER IN THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

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Abstract

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most common forms of malignant neoplasms in the world, which at the initial stage is almost asymptomatic, thereby making the process of diagnosing difficult. In the Republic of Belarus, over the past 10 years there has been a constant increase in the incidence of CRC.

This study analyzes the diagnostics, sickness and mortality rate from colorectal cancer in Minsk in 2016 and 2021 in different age groups of patients.

Keywords: colorectal cancer, symptoms, sickness rate, mortality rate, Minsk City Oncological dispensary, epidemiological data.

Introduction. In the structure of the incidence of oncological diseases, colorectal cancer (CRC) occupies one of the first positions. According to the official statistics of oncological diseases, in 2021 colorectal cancer (CRC) in Minsk ranked 2nd (16.1%), slightly second only to breast cancer (16.2%).

The purpose of this work is a comparative analysis of the sickness and mortality rate from colorectal cancer in Minsk based on various parameters.

Research materials and methods: the research material was the official statistical data of the Minsk City Clinical Dispensary on patients with colorectal cancer (CRC), collected at intervals of 5 years (for 2016 and 2021).

Results and discussion: The main risk factor for colorectal cancer in a formally healthy person is age [1]. Thus, the incidence of CRC in patients aged 40 years and younger is 8 cases per 100,000 of population,

and in people 60 years and older is 150 cases per 100,000 of population, and this applies to both men and women. 95% of patients with colorectal cancer in the UK are patients over 50 [2]. Of the 7 CIS countries, the highest sickness rate of CRC was registered in the Republic of Belarus, and the lowest in Uzbekistan.

According to the statistics of the Minsk City Clinical Dispensary, in 2016, CRC was first detected in 1,194 people (women – 52.7%; men – 47.3%), in 2021 – in 1,065 people (women – 48.5%; men – 51.5%). Thus, in 2016 and 2021, the diagnosis of CRC was made with approximately the same frequency for men and women. Using official statistics on the population in Minsk in 2016 (1,959,800) [3] and 2021 (2,009,786) [4], the incidence of CRC per 100,000 of population was calculated. In 2016, it was 60.9 cases, and in 2021 – 53.0.

The distribution of newly detected cases of colorectal cancer according to the age of patients in 2016 and in 2021 (the number of cases is indicated in parentheses) is approximately the same: in the age group 15-19 is 1 case (1), age group 20-24 – 0 (0) cases, age group 25-29 – 2 cases (1), age group 30-34 – 8 cases (4), age group 35-39 years – 18 (9) cases, age group 40-44 – 16 (23) cases, age group 45-49 – 33 (47) cases, age group 50-54 – 58 (37) cases, age group 55-59 – 135 (101) cases, age group 60-64 years – 163 (170) cases, age group 65-69 – 209 (188) cases, 70-74 years – 145 (213) cases, age group 75-79 – 218 (110) cases, age group 80-84 – 128 (103) cases, age group 85 years old and above – 60 cases (58). It can also be noted that if in 2016 the largest number of newly identified cases of CRC occurred in the age group of 75-79, then in 2021 it was 70-74 years of age.

In the course of the study, the figures for the detection of CRC in various stages were compared. In 2016, stage I cancer was diagnosed in 183 patients (15.3%), in stage II the disease was detected in 427 patients (35.7%), stage III cancer was diagnosed in 241 patients (20.2%), in stage IV – in 310 patients (26.0%), the stage was not established in 33 patients (2.8%). In 2021, stage I cancer was diagnosed in 153 patients (14.4%), in stage II – in 341 patients (32.0%), in stage III the disease was detected in 278 patients (26.1%), stage IV cancer was diagnosed in 277 patients (26.0%), the stage was not established in 16 patients (1.5%). Thus, the figures for the detection of CRC in 2016 and 5 years later are quite comparable.

As for the distribution of newly identified cases of CRC in accordance with the gender, 565 cases were detected in men in 2016, among them 544 cases with an established stage of the disease. Namely, stage I – 80 cases (14.2%), stage II – 202 cases (35.8%), stage III – 115 cases (20.4%), stage IV – 147 cases (26.0%), stage was not established in 21 cases (3.7%). Among women in 2016, 629 cases of CRC were detected, among which 617 cases with an established stage of the disease. Including, stage I – 103 cases (16.4%), stage II – 225 cases (35.8%), stage III – 126 cases (20.0%), stage IV – 163 cases (25.9%), stage was not established in 12 cases (1.9%). In 2021, 548 cases of CRC were detected, of which 541 cases with an established stage of the disease, including: stage I – 81 cases (14.8%), stage II – 173 cases (31.6%), stage III – 154 cases (28.1%), stage IV – 133 cases (24.3%), the stage is not established in 7 cases (1.3%). As for the 2021 there were 517 cases of CRC detected in women, among them there were 508 cases with the established stage of the disease, including stage I – 72 cases (13.9%), stage II – 168 cases (32.5%), stage III – 124 cases (24.0%), stage IV – 144 cases (27.9%), the stage has not been established in 9 cases (1.7%). Thus, both in 2016 and 5 years later, CRC is detected mainly in stage II (a third of all cases). In 2021, in comparison with 2016, there is a tendency to increase the detection of CRC in late stages (III and IV), which accounted for both men and women, totaling more than half of all cases of CRC.

As follows from the figures below, in general, CRC has been detected recently (2021) during preventive examinations (79.3%). In 2016, CRC was detected

preventive examinations only in 46.6%. Contacting a doctor due to the appearance of symptoms of CRC helped to identify the disease in 47.8% of cases in 2016 and in 16.9% of cases in 2021. In other cases, CRC was detected during the cancer screening, respectively, in 5.6% (2016) and 3.8% (2021).

The total number of men who died from CRC in 2016 was 303 and women – 250. At the same time, the peak of mortality in men (23.8%) was in the age group 65-69, in women (22.1%) – in the age group 75-79. In 2021, the total number of men who died from CRC was 236, and women – 241. The peak of mortality in men (22.1%) was the same as 5 years before at the age of 65-69 with almost the same indicators as in 2016 (22.1%). In women, the mortality rate from CRC in 2021 in the age group 75-79 was noticeably lower and amounted to only 9.1%. The maximum mortality from CRC in 2021 in women was in the age group of 85 years and older (16.6%) and in the age group 80-84 (14.9%). Thus, despite the comparability of figures in all stages of CRC in 2016 and 2021, there is a tendency to increase life expectancy in women with this type of cancer. It can be assumed that this is due to more modern and effective treatment. At the same time, the number of patients who received radical surgical treatment for 5 years has practically not changed. It was 58.8% (2016) of all patients with CRC and 55.5% (2021).

Conclusions. As a result of the study, it can be concluded that CRC occurred in 2016 and in 2021 with approximately the same frequency in both men and women.

In the analyzed years, the largest number of newly identified cases of CRC occurred in the age range of 70-79 years.

In 2021, compared with 2016, there is a tendency to increase the detection of CRC at late stages (III and IV), which accounted for more than half of all cases.

The effectiveness of preventive examinations for the detection of CRC has significantly increased in 2021 compared to 2016 and occupies a leading place in the detection of this oncological disease.

In 2021, compared with 2016, there is a tendency to increase life expectancy in women with CRC, which is probably due to more effective treatment.

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